

INCIDENCE OF HIV AND HBV INFECTIONS IN PATIENTS ATTENDING UNIVERSITY OF ADO EKITI TEACHING HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

Incidence of co-infection of HIV and HBV infections were determined in one thousand, three hundred and twenty four patients attending the University of Ado-Ekiti Teaching Hospital between January 2007 and May 2008. Out of this 411 (31%) were males while 913 (69%) were females. The samples collected from the patients were screened using DETERMINE and ACONS, HIV and HBV test kits respectively. A nil incidence was recorded for HIV with HBV. However, 26 (1.96%) of females and 19 (1.44%) of males were positive for HIV, while 43 (3.25%) of females and 23 (3.25%) of males were positive for HBV. The significance of this finding is discussed.

KEYWORDS: incidence, HIV, HBV co-infection, patients, teaching hospital

INTRODUCTION

Hepatitis B virus is reputed to be 50-100 times more infectious than HIV (Chessbrough, 2000). It's been said that if few drops of HBV-infected blood were dispensed into an Olympic sized standard swimming pool, the water of the swimming pool will still be infectious. That is despite the fact that such high volume of water would be far more than enough to dilute to extinction all other known infectious agents.

Acute hepatitis B resembles other forms of viral hepatitis and cannot be distinguished based on history, physical examination or serum biochemical tests (Beltrami *et al*, 2000). The diagnosis of acute HBV infection is confirmed by the demonstration of antibodies to hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg), in the serum which appears well before the outset of symptoms and before development of antibodies to hepatitis B core antigen (anti-HBc) and immunoglobulin M (IgM) antibody to HBC, which appear at approximately the same time as the symptoms (Hoofnagle and Biscelin, 1991, Irwin *et al*, 1975, Jemson *et al*, 1987).

The presence of IgM anti-HBc indicates recent HBV infection, usually within the preceding 4-6 month. The presence of hepatitis B antigen (HBcAg) in serum correlates with HBV replication high titres and infectivity. Persons who are positive for HBcAg typically have 10^8 to 10^9 HBV particles per ml of blood (Shikata *et al*, 1977. Tong and Trepo, 1997). In persons who resolve acute HBV infections, antibodies to HBsAg (anti-HBs) develop and indicate immunity. The persistence of HBsAg for six months after the diagnosis of acute HBV is indicative of progression to chronic HBV infection (Gordin *et al*, 1990; Gerberding 1994, Gupta *et al*, 1996; Schneiderman and Kaplan 1992, Turner *et al*, 1989, Donegan *et al*, 1992)

AIDS, the eventual terminus of unintercepted HIV progression is known to open the door to other infections, especially the opportunistic ones. The consequences of HIV and HBV co-infection could be very fatal. Jindal, *et al*, (2008) determined the prevalence of HIV, hepatitis B and C co-infections in Amritsar, Northern India. Three groups of population at high risk of HIV infections (injecting drug users, IDUs, truckers and attendees of STD clinic of Amritsar) were studied to determine prevalence of HIV, hepatitis B and C co-infections. Of the 157 IDUs, 16.6%, 17.8% and 33.7% were found to be positive for HIV, HBV and HCV respectively. HCV showed significant difference ($P < 0.01$) and very high rate (8.3%) of co-infection with HIV. In truckers, they found that maximum seropositivity was associated with HIV (19%) i-e significantly higher than that of HBV (6%, $P < 0.01$) and HCV (3%, $P < 0.01$). In the STD clinic

attendees, the highest ratio of seroprevalence was that of HIV (4.3%) followed closely by that of HBV (3.7%) and HCV (2.6%).

This present study was aimed at determining the prevalence of HIV and HBV co-infections among voluntary and commercial blood donors, patients attending various clinics and those on admission at University of Ado-Ekiti Teaching Hospital, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

MATERIALS AND METHOD

STUDY SITE

The study was carried out at the University of Ado-Ekiti Teaching Hospital, Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State in south west Nigeria. The study was carried out between January 2007 and May, 2008.

SAMPLE COLLECTION

Venous blood samples were collected from a total of one thousand three hundred and twenty-four subjects. The subjects composed of four hundred and eleven males (31%) and nine hundred and thirteen females (69%) with ages ranging between two day old and 83 years. The subjects were voluntary and commercial blood donors, in-patients and out-patients of the University of Ado-Ekiti Teaching Hospital.

The sera of the samples were separated out after spinning the samples in the centrifuge for two minutes at 5000rpm.

Retroviral Screening

The samples were screened for the presence or otherwise of antibodies to HIV, using a reliable immunochromatographic test-kit DETERMINE. This detected the presence of or otherwise of antibodies to HIV based on the number of colour bands that appeared in the test and control areas at the end of the test.

Hepatitis Screening

Similarly, the samples were screened for the presence or otherwise of antibodies to HBsAg, using ACONS^(R) test-kit, which also utilized the principles of immunochromatography to HBsAg based on the number of colour-bands that appeared in the test and control areas of the test kit.

RESULT

Forty-five out of the one thousand three hundred and twenty four subjects screened for both HIV and HBV, were HIV positive, representing on overall HIV seroprevalence of 3.4%.

Table 1: HIV Seroprevalence among the sexes

	Female	Male	Total
HIV (Negative)	887 (66.9%)	392 (29.6%)	1279 (96.6%)
HIV (Positive)	26 (1.96%)	19 (1.44%)	45 (%)
	913 (69%)	411 (31%)	1324 (3.4%)

Twenty-six (1.96%) females out of the one thousand three hundred and twenty-four subjects were positive for HIV, while nineteen (%) males were HIV positive,

Table 2: HBV seroprevalence among the sexes

	Female	Male	Total
Hepatitis B (Negative)	870 (65.9%)	388 (29.3%)	1258 (95%)
Hepatitis B (Positive)	43 (3.25%)	23 (3.25%)	66(4.9% %)
	913	411	1324

A total of sixty-six (4.98%) out of one thousand three hundred and twenty four subjects tested positive for hepatitis B, Out of this figure, forty-three (3.25%) were females, while twenty three (1.74%) were males.

The age distribution among the 45 HIV seropositive subjects, shows that six (13.3%) were under 15 years (these were mostly infants who were victims of vertical HIV transmission from their mothers). Thirty eight (84.4%) were between 16-60years and one (2.22%) was 62 years old representing 2.22% (see table 3)

Table 3: HIV and HBV Seroprevalence among age-groups

AGE	DISEASE	
	HIV	Hepatitis
Under 15	6 (13.3%)	4 (6.1%)
16 – 60 yrs	38 (84.4%)	52 (78.8%)
76 yrs	1 (2.22%)	10 (15.2%)
Total	45	66

The age distribution among the sixty-six hepatitis B positive subjects reveals that four (6.1%) were under 15 years old, fifty-two (78.8%) were aged between 16-60 years and ten (15.2%) were 60 years and above.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

A most startling revelation of this study is the discovery that the incidence of HIV and HBV co-infection in Ado-Ekiti is nil. This contrasts sharply with recent similar studies carried out by Pontali and Ferrari (2008) in Genoa Prison, Italy. They reported an alarming 90% HIV and HCV (hepatitis C) co-infection and also 6.7% HIV/HBV/HCV triple infections among the inmates of Genoa Prison in Italy.

Also this study is in total agreement with that of Jindal *et al* (2008). They also recorded a nil incidence of HIV/HBV co-infection in their study carried out in Amristar, India, However, Hoffman and Thio (2007) think HIV/HBV co-infection is not uncommon.

Why the incidence of HIV/HBV co-infection in Ado-Ekiti is nil is a nagging question that has been thrown up by this study and this can only be answered by further investigations.

Be that as it may however, this study equally throws up another very vital issue of public concern. This study has found the overall HIV seroprevalence to be 3.4% whereas the official figure for the state is 1.6% (FMOH, 2007). While the Federal Government-driven nationwide HIV sentinel survey uses only pregnant women attending government antenatal clinics (FMOH, 2007), this study used subjects of different ages (2 days to 83 years) from different background and social classes. This shows that the biennially conducted nationwide sentinel survey is not a true reflection of the real state of HIV seropositivity in Ekiti State and of course the whole country Relevant federal authorities are advised to re-design the biennial HIV/syphilis sentinel survey to include subjects of different age groups and social classes and not just pregnant women attending government antenatal clinics.

REFERENCES

- Beltrami EM, Williams I.T, Shapiro CN and Chamberland M.E, (2000). *Risk and Management of Blood – borne infections in Health care Workers. Clin Microbiol Rev.* 13,3,385-407
- Chessbrough M, (2000). *District Laboratory Practice in Tropical Countries*, 250 – 251. Cambridge University Press, UK.
- Donegan S.P, Steger K.A, Recla L, Huff R.S, Werner B.G, Rice P.A and Craven D.E, (1992). *Seroprevalence of human immunodeficiency virus in parturient at Boston City Hospital: Implications for public health and obstetric practice.* Am J. Obstet. Gynaecol, 167, 622 – 629
- Federal Ministry of Health (2007). *Official Report of 2005 National HIV/Syphilis Sentinel Survey*, Abuja, Nigeria.

Gerberding J.L, (1994). *Incidence and prevalence of Human immunodeficiency virus, hepatitis B virus, hepatitis C virus and cytomegalovirus among healthcare personnel at risk for blood exposure: Final report from a longitudinal study.* J infect Dis 170, 1410 – 1417

Gordan F.M, Gilbert C, Hawley H.P and Willoughby A. (1990). *Prevalence of human immunodeficiency virus and hepatitis B virus in unselected hospital admissions. Implications for mandatory testing and universal precautions.* J. Infect Dis 161, 14 – 17

Guptan R.C, Thakur V, Sarin S.K, Benerjee K and Khandekar P, (1996.) *Frequency and clinical profile of precore and surface hepatitis B mutants in Asian – Indian patients with chronic liver disease.* Am J Gastroenterol 91, 1312 – 1317

Hoffman CJ and Thio CL (2008). *Clinical implications of HIV and Hepatitis B co - infection in Asia and Africa.* Lancet Infect Dis Apr 8 (4) 210 – 211.

Hoofnagole JH and Bisceqline Am, (1991), *Serological diagnosis of acute and chronic viral hepatitis.* Semin. Liver Dis, 11, 79 – 83

Irwin G.R, Allen AM, Bancroft W.H, Karwack, JJ, Brown H.L, Pinkerton RH, Willight M and Top F.H Jr, (1975). *Hepatitis B antigen in saliva, urine and stool.* Infect Immun 11, 142 – 145

Jewson SA, Lemon SM, Baker L.N and Newbold J.E, (1987). *Qualitative analysis of hepatitis B. Urine DNA in saliva and semen of chronically infected homosexual men* J. Inject Dis, 156, 299 – 307.

Jindal N, Arora U and Singh K, (2008). *Prevalence of human immunodeficiency virus HIV, hepatitis B virus and hepatitis C virus in three groups of populations at high risk of HIV infection in Amritsar (Punjab), Northern India.* J infect Dis, Jan 61 (1), 79 – 81

Pontali E and Ferrari F, (2008). *Prevalence of Hepatitis B virus and/or Hepatitis C Virus co-infection in prisoners infected with HIV.* Int. J Prison Health June 4 (2) 77 – 82.

Schneiderman LJ and Kaplan RM, (1992). *Fear of dying and HIV infection versus hepatitis B infection.* AM J. Infect Control 82, 584 – 586

Shikata T.T, Karasawa T, Abe K, Uzawa T, Suzuki H, Oda T, Imai M, Mayumi M and Montsuyu Y. (1977). *Hepatitis B antigen and infectivity of hepatitis B virus.* J. infects Dis, 136, 571 – 576.

Tong S. and Trepo (1997) *The HBe-minus mutants of hepatitis B virus.* Pp 89-104 In Harrison T.J. and Zuckerman A.J., *The molecular medicine of viral hepatitis.* John Willey and Sons, Ltd. Chichester, United Kingdom.

Turner S.B, Kunches LM, Gordon K.F, Travers PH and Mueller N.E, (1989). *Occupational exposure to human immunodeficiency virus and hepatitis B virus among embalmers: a pilot seroprevalence study.* Am J public Health 79, 1425 – 1426

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